

**MORAL VALUES OF MEDIEVAL ISLAMIC PHILOSOPHY:
ESSENCE, IMPORTANCE IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE
INDIVIDUAL AND SOCIETY**

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes the role of moral values of **Middle Ages Eastern Renaissance Eastern philosophy, as well as Islamic philosophy in the spiritual education of a person and sustainable development of society.**

Key words: Medieval Eastern Renaissance , Islamic philosophy, spiritual education, moral values, sustainable development.

Enter

The IX-XII centuries were a period of rapid development of science, culture, and social life in Central Asia, the Middle East , and entered the pages of human history under the terms "first" or "first Muslim Renaissance". The scientific and spiritual legacy of the great encyclopedic scholars of Central Asia, such as Musa al-Khorazmi, Abu Nasr Faro bi, Abu Abdullah Khorazmi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, who lived and worked in this period. It was important in the further development of Ahan science, culture and civilization. The worldview of great thinkers was formed within the values of Islamic philosophy and became an important phenomenon of the Eastern Renaissance.

Today, the world scientific community acknowledges that in the rich spiritual heritage of the great scientists of Central Asia, not only the religious and natural

sciences, but also the mutual harmony of nature and society, the priority of spiritual values, and the philosophical issues of personal perfection have found their detailed explanation.

The main part

understand , first of all, the spiritual and philosophical heritage of Central Asian, Middle Eastern and Middle Eastern thinkers formed on the basis of Islamic values within the framework of Islamic civilization . Great sages and encyclopedic scientists like Muhammad Khorezmi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ibn Sina, and Ulug'bek, who came from Central Asia, made a great contribution to the development of our civilization and to the creation of the foundation of our modern sciences, especially mathematics, astronomy, medicine, and philosophy. Their rich spiritual heritage is first of all based on the spiritual values of Islam, and in them the mutual harmony of nature and society, the priority of spiritual values, and issues related to personal perfection have found their detailed explanation.

The philosophical heritage of our great ancestors was characterized by the following important features:

- his time, but based on perception, creative development of them;
- rationalism: the development of the science of logic, acceptance of reason as a criterion of the validity of knowledge;
- consideration of speech and reason as an important factor in strengthening faith, resulting in the development of secular and religious sciences without opposing each other, the harmony of religious and secular sciences;

— the doctrine that faith is manifested in good behavior, moral maturity is an important factor determining the human perspective - the development of moral philosophy;

— the essence of humanism and enlightenment, their harmony; the creation of fair society and state models on this basis;

— It is distinguished by the fact that it is manifested in the development of literature, calligraphy, painting, architecture, art of recitation, aesthetic taste and artistic thinking .

These features are the basis for the vitality and sustainability of Islamic philosophy for centuries.

Islamic philosophy can be divided into the following main areas: 1. Philosophy of the word. 2. The philosophy of nature. 3. Sufism philosophy. 4. Enlightenment philosophy.

Kalam philosophy is characterized by looking at the issues of man, his life and destiny from the point of view of moderate theological principles and logical thinking, combining theological traditions with the principles of rationality, verbal and intellectual knowledge. According to this doctrine, behavior is created by God, but acquired and performed by a person who has free will .

Abu Mansur Moturudi, who founded the teaching of the word in Movarounnahr, divided the knowledge of the world into two types: ancient and hadith knowledge. Knowledge of the ancients means to know God, and knowledge of hadith means to understand the creatures. Professional knowledge is also divided into historical and rational (i.e. mental) knowledge. Knowledge created through communication is called historical, and knowledge based on reason is called historical.

Moturidi recognized that a person can know something only by studying and examining existing things. According to him, knowledge can be acquired through experience and observation developed under the mind and its control; experience

is only part of understanding the nature of things. The other parts are made up of intelligence and mental elements. Reason is the last and at the same time limited right given to man. For this reason, there are things that cannot be known by reason and experience, which can be generated through other information. Among such information, Moturidi included the moments of inspiration that can be born in the human heart. He believed that man is a divine being because of his ability to think.

The representatives of Kalam philosophy are God and the world, the structure of bodies in nature; who analyzed issues such as the direct connection of human life and future with his morality from the point of view of rational thinking.

Major Central Asian representatives of Kalam philosophy: Abu Mansur Moturidi (853-944); Mahmud Zamakhshari (1075 - 1144) and others.

The philosophy of naturalism (or mashshoiyun) is characterized by looking at the issues of the universe, man and his thinking from the point of view of mutual harmony of religious and natural science, and high evaluation of the spiritual, educational, and educational importance of science and religion in society. Representatives of natural philosophy have encyclopedic knowledge . ***They made a great contribution to the development of*** natural science , the classification of scientific knowledge and scientific research methods, and the formation of the European renaissance. Those who developed the models of a just virtuous society and its management.

Major representatives of natural philosophy from Central Asia: Abu Nasr Farabi (873-950); Abu Abdullah Khorezmi (d. 997); Abu Rayhan Beruni (973-1048); Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037); Ismail Jurjani (died about 1137); Chagmini (died about 1221) and others.

The philosophy of Sufism. Sufism is a separate religious-philosophical worldview formed within the framework of Islam, according to which a person can

establish direct spiritual communication with God through his personal spiritual experience. For this, a person who has love for God in his heart can *purify his soul from the rust of selfishness* and thereby ensure his involvement in the Supreme Truth. The "path" of Sufism consists of spiritual purification and perfection of a person based on stable moral principles (maqamot) and inner mental state (hal) as a momentary spark of divine light. **Irfan** is a theory of Sufism, a mystical direction of understanding the reality of existence.

Major figures of Sufism philosophy: Ahmad Yassavi (d. 1166); Abdulhaliq Ghijduvani (d. 1179); Bahavuddin Naqshband (1318-1383); Najmuddin Kubro (1145-1221); Jalaluddin Rumi (1207-1273) and others. have been

Enlightenment philosophy is a huge spiritual heritage of the peoples of Central Asia during the stage of Islamic Enlightenment, which reflected the mystical, philosophical, socio-ethical values in scientific and artistic-symbolic forms. According to him, spirituality is the manifestation of God's Truth hidden in human language . In order for the human soul to maintain its constant harmony with the Reality of Being, it is required to learn a profession and science, to work honestly, to always keep the mirror of the mind clean through love and loyalty, enlightenment . It embodies the ideas that mutual harmony of sciences, principles of humanism and enlightened existence, manifestation of faith in beautiful behavior, moral perfection is an important factor determining human perspective.

The representatives of the Enlightenment philosophy are great creative workers and thinkers who, with their works, have made a great contribution to the spread of high spiritual values among the masses and to the formation of a unique oriental way of thinking .

Major figures of Enlightenment philosophy : Yusuf Khos Hajib (XI century); Sa'diddin Taftazani (1322-1392); Abdurrahman Jami (1414-1492); Alisher Navoi (1441-1501); Husayn Voiz Koshifi (1440-1504); Mirzo Bedil (1644-1721) and others.

It is worth noting that the teachings of our great ancestors about existence, knowledge of the universe, classification of sciences, fair society, and the integrality of education and training in achieving human happiness influenced the Renaissance period of Europe. The ideas and concepts reflected in the examples of our cultural and spiritual heritage created by our ancestors are important today in solving not only social and spiritual problems, but also problems of a global nature.

CONCLUSION

In modernizing Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to studying the values of Islamic religion, philosophy and culture. In particular, on the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoev, the establishment of the Islamic Civilization Center in Tashkent under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Imam Bukhari in Samarkand, and Imam Termizi international research centers in Termiz are of historical importance.

In these centers, the scientific, philosophical, and spiritual heritage of scientists, thinkers, and scholars from Central Asia is being studied in depth; special attention is paid to revealing their humanitarian and enlightened nature, highlighting their place in historical and modern civilization, and promoting the spiritual courage of our great ancestors.

Cooperation of specialists of different countries in this field serves to solve the global problems facing humanity. As the great thinker and encyclopedic scholar Abu Nasr Farabi said: "... nations and peoples whose representatives cooperate in the path of universal happiness in all cities are perfect nations and peoples. In this way, if the people of the world cooperate and help each other, the Earth will be perfect and become a place of goodness. " [1.B.115; B.187] . If we compare the thoughts of Abu Nasr Farabi with our reality today, it is possible to find opportunities to prevent global threats and reduce their impact with the joint efforts of the world's leading like-minded representatives.

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